

LEXICAL-SEMANTIC AND METHODOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF DIPLOMATIC TEXTS

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Abstract: In this thesis, comments are made about the lexical-semantic and methodological features of the texts used in diplomatic relations.

Key words: Linguistics, lexical methodology, scientific analysis, linguistic analysis, terminology, international communication.

It is known from linguistics that the lexical-semantic form of any language involves the coverage of almost all areas of knowledge about the world, lexical-semantic and stylistic features serve to fluently reflect international words in our language, and thereby benefit from the achievements of science. opens the possibility of productive use. Classification and description of field terms, their linguistic analysis in the context of different systematic languages, identification and development of methods, methods and methodologies for analysis of lexical-semantic and methodological features of diplomatic texts are among the important issues facing world linguists.

It is worth noting that for the active development of the lexicon of diplomacy in the Uzbek language, it is logical to determine the results of a person's mental activity related to diplomacy and foreign state relations. Today, it is commendable that scientists and researchers are conducting a lot of theoretical and scientific work on the tendency to re-analyze the lexical-semantic and methodological units of diplomacy in the Uzbek language. In general, such diligent efforts are distinguished by the fact that they are aimed at preserving the purity of the Uzbek language, restoring its original nature, as well as the significant role of other languages, the patterns of lexical units, their it requires to carry out scientific research, which implies its structure, content, etymology and use in speech.

It is known that the Vienna Convention was developed on April 18, 1961 in Vienna at the UN Conference "On Issues of Diplomatic Relations and Immunities" regarding the standardization of diplomacy and political lexicons. This legal document, which consists of 53 articles, defines the status and tasks of diplomatic missions under the heads of states.

Diplomatic texts are a set of various official letters and diplomatic documents. A tool for conducting relations between states, one of the main forms of foreign political and diplomatic activity of the state. Correspondence between states is carried out on behalf of the state, the head of government, the foreign affairs office, various state and public organizations and institutions or their heads, diplomatic representatives and some diplomats. Letters, telegrams, letters, correspondence by notes, as well as declarations, summons, messages of information agents are types of diplomatic correspondence. Diplomatic texts cover issues of international life and foreign policy, bilateral or multilateral relations between states. Preparation of these documents is considered an important area of diplomatic activity of the state and related institutions.

A diplomatic act is a written text that is handed over or sent by the foreign relations authorities of one country to the foreign relations authorities of another country. The most common diplomatic acts are notes, memoranda and communiques. diplomatic letter. Note - an official address of one state to the government of another state; a document whose content should be seriously and urgently considered. A note is a diplomatic act by which a right or claim can be declared, a protest against the wrongdoing of another government. Notes, like other official diplomatic documents, do not contain direct consent or protest, but can be informative. But even in this case, they have a certain legal significance: the fact indicated in the note in a certain formula represents the official point of view of this government. The note should be short in content, without unnecessary phrases, carefully edited.

There is a specific protocol for drafting any diplomatic document. This is a written tribute to the addressee. As a rule, a diplomatic document begins and ends with a received social compliment. The rules of speech etiquette are important in business correspondence. Well-written letters leave a positive impression on the sender.

The nature and development of these texts are studied in two directions - historical and methodological. In the historical-methodical direction, not only the content of speech tools is studied, but also the law of their use in different text types. Due to the breadth and diversity of the scope of the diplomatic text, its content is also diverse. They differ from each other in the selection and use of lexical-phraseological and grammatical tools.

Each of the diplomatic texts is distinguished by the fact that it serves one or another area of social life and belongs to a certain sphere of practical human activity. Therefore, they are related to a certain field of speech activity.

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